

**LINGUISTIC CLASSIFICATION OF ADJECTIVES IN PARTS OF
SPEECH**

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Abstract: In this article, we have analyzed in detail the place of word groups in the language system in English and Uzbek languages, the main criteria in the studies devoted to word groups in linguistics, and the linguistic laws put forward by English linguists.

Key words: Part of speech, morphological features cognitive linguistics, scientific and special terminology, grammatical meaning.

In 170-90 BC, Dionysius Thrax, a representative of the Alexandrian school, analyzed the eight word groups (noun, verb, adjective, article, pronoun, auxiliary, adverb, conjunction) for the ancient Greek language, and he also expressed his views on the division of word groups. stands out: "A noun is a group of words that expresses a body or thing and general and specific: general, for example, a person, specific - for example, Socrates" recording of 8 word groups is observed in the XVI-XVII centuries (in Slavic languages). We can see that this is also reflected in the famous Russian Grammar by M. V. Lomonosov. Also, the adjective has been replaced by an adjective phrase (Vostokov). R.P. Pavsky and F.I. Buslaev separately include the number group in this line, in the 20th century in Russian linguistics, prepositions also took a strong place among the word groups. The system consists of 10 categories. L.L. Bulanin used certain analyzes to define the criteria for distinguishing word groups. They note the semantic and grammatical basis. Here we can see that the meaning of the word group is defined by different scholars with different terms: ("basic meaning" - A.M. Zemsky; "general, abstract meaning" A.I.

Smarnitsky; "generalized meaning" - modern Russian language, 1964 ; "generalized - abstract meaning" - A.V. Dudnikov; "lexical-grammatical meaning" - N.S. Valgina; "categorical meaning" - grammar - 1970; "classifying meaning" - A.N. Tikhonov; "grammatical meaning" "-A.N. Gvozdev, Steblin - Kamensky), but if the term "lexical meaning" is chosen for the essence of the phenomenon, it is more appropriate to note it as a grammatical basis if the morphological and syntactic criteria are combined in the classification.

The book "Current Uzbek language (phonetics, lexicology, morphology)" published in 1966 analyzed the theoretical data on the classification of word groups. It was initially given as "group of independent and auxiliary words". Also, if the exclamations that make up a separate group are studied by dividing them into mimemes, figurative and modal words, the noun group is the most common among the groups, and from the adjective, number, and verb word groups, the grammatical categories are also the syntactic functions that they perform in the sentence. , without division, we can see the categories of tense and mood. In addition, it was noted that there are categories such as degree, transitive-intransitive, personality-impersonality. The word group Ravish indicates a sign characteristic of adjectives. It does not accept adjectives and adverbs. We can also see that they do not change, do not adapt to the word they are associated with, and do not control them.

Published in 1975 by U. Tursunov J. Mukhtorov. In Sh. Rakhmatullaev's manual entitled "Current Uzbek Literary Language", the word is divided into 5 groups depending on the meaning and grammatical signs: 1) independent words; 2) auxiliary words; 3) modal words; 4) exclamations; 5) imitative words are implied. It was mentioned that independent words have lexical meaning understanding, functioning as part of a sentence, and possessing features of word creation, form creation, and word change.

Published by Sh. Shoabdurakhmonov, M. Askarova, A. Khojiev, I. Rasulov, Kh. Doniyorov. In the "Current Uzbek Literary Language" textbook, word groups

are divided into 12 types, independent words - noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb, adverb; auxiliary words - helper, linker, load; apart from that we can see that it is learned in the form of modal words, interjections and similes. If we look at other literature, we can see that in the book "Practicum of Uzbek language grammar" the word groups are divided into four big groups:

1. Independent words - noun, adjective, number, pronoun, adverb.
2. Auxiliary words - auxiliary, linking, loading.
3. Exclamatory and imitation words.
4. Modal words.

It was mentioned that the words are distinguished from each other according to their morphological signs and syntactic function in the sentence. If the words expressing the concept of object are nouns, agreement, possessive, number categories, the words expressing action or state have such categories as transitive-intransitive, inclination, tense, person-number, other words are said not to have such a feature.

We can see that word groups have been treated differently in all languages of the world and that linguists have expressed their scientific views. In the textbook "Introduction to Linguistics" published in 1981 by A.Sodikov, A.Abdulazizov, and M.Iriskulov, it is aimed to study word groups in comparison with other languages - English, German and French, and to pay more attention to their essence. mentioned as having:

1. Categorical signs of word groups.
2. Principles of classification of words.
3. Phrases of different languages.

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